

Supplemental Material

Considerations on activity determinants of fungal polyphenol oxidases based on mutational and structural studies

**Efstratios Nikolaivits^{1#}, Alexandros Valmas^{2#}, Grigorios Dedes¹, Evangelos Topakas¹,
Maria Dimarogona^{3*}**

¹*Industrial Biotechnology & Biocatalysis Group, Biotechnology Laboratory, School of Chemical Engineering, National Technical University of Athens, Athens, Greece*

²*Department of Biology, University of Patras, Patras, Greece*

³*Laboratory of Structural Biology and Biotechnology, Department of Chemical Engineering, University of Patras, Patras, Greece*

*Correspondence to: M. Dimarogona, *Department of Chemical Engineering, University of Patras, University Campus, Patras 26504, Greece*

E-mail address: mdimarog@chemeng.upatras.gr, Tel.: +30 2610 969514

[#]Efstratios Nikolaivits and Alexandros Valmas contributed equally to this work. Author order was determined by E.N.'s seniority.

Figure S1 Relative activity of *TiPPO* variants (G292N: red; L306A: green; Y296V: yellow; G292N/L306A: blue and G292N/Y296V: magenta) on various phenolic compounds compared to the WT. For L-tyrosine and *p*-hydroxy(OH)phenylacetic acid, relative activity is calculated based on the variant with the highest activity, since WT could not utilize these compounds. Reactions took place at 35 °C for 20 h at 5 mM substrate concentration in pH 7.

Figure S2 (A) SDS-PAGE gel of *TtPPO-GN* submitted to crystallization trials. FL corresponds to full length and Tr to truncated *TtPPO-GN* and (B) crystals of full length *TtPPO-GN*.

Figure S3 SDS gel of WT *TtPPO* and its variants, including a prestained protein marker (M). The yield for each variant in mg per liter of culture was: 39.4 for WT; 64.3 for G292N; 20.3 for L306A; 44.0 for Y296V; 21.0 for G292N/L306A; 21.9 for G292N/Y296V.